

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

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ABSTRACT

Background: Platelet consumption and leukocyte activation are integral to the host response in sepsis, yet the prognostic relevance of serial platelet and white blood cell (WBC) trends in surgical septic patients admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) remains clinically important. This study evaluated whether platelet indices and WBC indices were associated with ICU mortality in adult surgical septic patients.

Objective: To evaluate the association between platelet count and ICU mortality and to correlate platelet and WBC measures among surgical septic patients admitted to intensive care unit.

Methods: This is a single-center hospital-based observational analytical study that included 57 patients with surgical sepsis who were admitted to the intensive care unit (ICU) at No. (1) Military Hospital (700 bedded), Pyin Oo Lwin, from 01/01/2025 to 31/12/2025. Admission values were defined as ICU Day 1 (D1). Platelet nadir was the lowest platelet count recorded from ICU Day 1 to ICU Day 14, and peak WBC was the highest WBC recorded over the same period. The primary endpoint was intra-ICU mortality. Additional derived variables were absolute platelet fall, absolute WBC rise, timing of platelet nadir, and timing of WBC peak. Continuous variables were summarized as median and interquartile range (IQR), compared using the Mann-Whitney U test, and correlations were assessed using Spearman rho. Categorical variables were compared using Fisher exact test or chi-square test where appropriate. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis with the Youden index was used to identify optimal cut-offs for ICU mortality prediction. A predefined combined platelet-WBC risk group was additionally tested using platelet nadir $\leq 90 \times 10^9/L$ and peak WBC $\geq 22.3 \times 10^9/L$. Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 28.0.

Results: Of the 57 patients, 22 died in ICU, yielding an ICU mortality of 38.6%. Non-survivors were older than survivors (median age 58.0 (35.0-68.0) vs 47.0 (40.0-52.0), $p = 0.039$) and had longer ICU stays (10.0 (6.0-17.0) vs 6.0 (3.0-8.0), $p = 0.002$). The admission platelet count was lower in non-survivors, but the difference was not statistically significant (median 140.0 (104.0-222.0) vs 160.0 (133.0-380.0), $p = 0.222$). Platelet nadir was markedly lower in non-survivors (37.5 (20.0-81.5) vs 93.0 (79.0-165.5), $p < 0.001$), and the absolute platelet fall was greater ($p = 0.027$). The timing of platelet nadir occurred substantially later in non-survivors (median 6.0 (4.0-8.0) vs 2.0 (2.0-4.5), $p < 0.001$). Mortality increased across platelet nadir categories (chi-square $p = 0.002$). Admission WBC did not differ significantly ($p = 0.113$), whereas peak WBC was significantly higher in non-survivors (32.1 (26.4-42.2) vs 20.5 (15.7-30.9), $p = 0.002$). In the overall, platelet nadir showed a weak inverse but non-significant correlation with peak WBC (rho -0.098, $p = 0.469$), whereas platelet nadir correlated positively with admission WBC (rho 0.325, $p = 0.014$). On ROC analysis, platelet nadir demonstrated the best platelet-based discrimination (AUC 0.768) with an optimal cut-off of $90.0 \times 10^9/L$, while peak WBC showed

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
28 May 2026

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

the best leukocyte-based discrimination (AUC 0.743) with a cut-off of $22.3 \times 10^9/L$. When these thresholds were combined, ICU mortality was 0.0% in the low-risk group, 29.2% in the intermediate-risk group, and 71.4% in the high-risk group (chi-square $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: In surgical sepsis, dynamic hematologic markers outperformed admission values. A low platelet nadir and high peak WBC were each associated with ICU mortality, and their combination created clinically meaningful mortality risk stratification. Platelet trajectory, particularly the nadir and its delayed occurrence, deserves routine integration into the ICU sepsis assessment rather than reliance on a single admission platelet value.

KEYWORDS: Surgical sepsis, platelet count, platelet nadir, thrombocytopenia, white blood cell count, ICU mortality, ROC curve, risk stratification.

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INTRODUCTION

Sepsis remains one of the leading causes of mortality among critically ill surgical patients worldwide. According to the Sepsis-3 definition, sepsis is characterized by a dysregulated host response to infection resulting in life-threatening organ dysfunction (1,2). Surgical patients are particularly vulnerable because of tissue injury, contamination, delayed source control, repeated operations, postoperative physiological stress, and metabolic burden associated with critical illness. These factors contribute to systemic inflammatory activation and poor clinical outcomes (3).

Routine laboratory investigations play an important role in bedside assessment of septic patients. Among these investigations, platelet count and white blood cell (WBC) count are inexpensive, rapidly available, and frequently repeated parameters in intensive care practice. Despite their routine use, the prognostic significance of serial platelet and WBC trends in surgical sepsis remains incompletely understood (2,3).

Platelets are traditionally recognized for their role in hemostasis. However, increasing evidence has demonstrated that platelets also participate in immune regulation, endothelial stability, inflammatory signaling, microvascular perfusion, and immunothrombosis. During sepsis, thrombocytopenia may result from platelet consumption, disseminated intravascular coagulation, endothelial injury, immune-mediated destruction, bone marrow suppression, and inflammation-associated platelet activation. Therefore, thrombocytopenia in septic patients is increasingly regarded as a marker of disease severity rather than an isolated hematologic abnormality (3,4).

Several previous studies have shown that thrombocytopenia is associated with prolonged ICU stay, organ dysfunction, and increased mortality in septic patients. Importantly, platelet kinetics appear to provide greater prognostic value than admission platelet count alone. Patients may initially present with normal platelet counts but subsequently develop severe thrombocytopenia during ICU admission, whereas others may recover rapidly following an early decline. Consequently, platelet nadir, extent of platelet fall,

and platelet recovery pattern may better reflect the biological progression of sepsis (4-8,12).

White blood cell count has similarly long been used as a marker of inflammation and infection in septic patients. Leukocytosis may indicate persistent inflammatory activation, uncontrolled infection, postoperative complications, or inadequate source control, whereas leukopenia may reflect immune exhaustion and overwhelming sepsis. Similar to platelet count, the prognostic importance of WBC count may depend more on serial trends than on a single admission measurement. Persistently elevated WBC values during ICU stay have been associated with poor septic outcomes and increased mortality (9-11,14,15).

Although platelet abnormalities and leukocyte responses are both important in sepsis, many previous studies evaluated these variables separately or focused mainly on mixed medical ICU populations. Surgical sepsis differs because inflammatory burden may arise from gastrointestinal perforation, bowel ischemia, biliary contamination, peritonitis, anastomotic leakage, necrosis, malignancy, and repeated operative interventions. Therefore, combined assessment of platelet and WBC dynamics may provide a more practical and clinically meaningful method of risk stratification in surgical septic ICU patients (3,16).

The present study was conducted to evaluate the association between platelet count and ICU mortality and to assess the relationship between platelet and WBC measures in surgical septic patients admitted to intensive care unit. The study also aimed to determine ROC-derived cut-off values for hematologic predictors of ICU mortality and to evaluate whether a combined platelet-WBC risk model could improve bedside risk stratification in surgical sepsis.

Aim

To evaluate the association between platelet count and mortality and to correlate platelet and WBC counts in relation to mortality in surgical septic patients admitted to intensive care unit.

Objectives

- To describe patient characteristics and ICU mortality.

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

- To compare admission platelet count and platelet nadir between survivors and non-survivors.
- To compare admission and peak WBC counts between survivors and non-survivors.
- To assess the correlation between platelet and WBC measures.
- To determine ROC-based cut-offs for platelet and WBC predictors of ICU mortality.
- To assess the association between combined platelet-WBC risk group and ICU mortality.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

This is a single-center hospital-based prospective observational analytical study. This study was conducted in the surgical intensive care unit of No. (1) Military Hospital (700 bedded) in Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar. The recruitment start date was 01/01/2025, and the end date was 31/12/2025. Adult patients with clinical diagnosis of surgical sepsis, availability of baseline platelet and WBC counts, and ICU admission were included in the study. Patients with known hematological disorders, chronic liver disease with hypersplenism, chemotherapy or immunosuppressant exposure, or incomplete data were excluded from the study. Informed written consent explaining the research procedure was obtained after admission to the ICU. The minimum required sample size for this study was 48 patients. A total of 57 patients were allocated in the study period.

Admission WBC and admission platelet were taken from ICU Day 1. Platelet nadir was defined as the minimum platelet count from ICU Day 1 through ICU Day 14. Peak WBC was defined as the maximum WBC value over the same period. Platelet nadir categories were defined as severe ($<50 \times 10^9/L$), moderate ($50-99 \times 10^9/L$), mild ($100-149 \times 10^9/L$), and normal ($\geq 150 \times 10^9/L$).

Two additional dynamic variables were derived: absolute platelet fall (platelet nadir minus admission platelet count) and absolute WBC rise (peak WBC minus admission WBC). Additional derived variables were absolute platelet fall, absolute WBC rise, timing of platelet nadir, and timing of WBC peak. The primary endpoint was intra-ICU mortality. The ICU outcome was classified as survivor or non-survivor according to the intra-ICU mortality.

Continuous variables were summarized using median and interquartile range. Group comparisons between survivors and non-survivors were performed using the Mann-Whitney U test. Categorical variables were compared using Fisher exact test or chi-square test where appropriate. Correlations between platelet and WBC variables were assessed using Spearman rho.

ROC analysis was used to evaluate the discriminatory ability of admission platelet, platelet nadir, admission WBC, and peak WBC for ICU mortality, and optimal thresholds were determined using the Youden index. Lower platelet values were treated as higher-risk values in ROC scoring.

The combined platelet-WBC risk group followed the predefined protocol thresholds: platelet nadir $\leq 90 \times 10^9/L$ together with peak WBC $\geq 22.3 \times 10^9/L$. Patients with neither threshold were low risk, those with one threshold were intermediate risk, and those with both thresholds were high risk. All data were recorded in a proforma for each patient. Statistical analysis was performed on a total of 57 patients by using IBM SPSS® Statistics version 28.0. A two-sided p value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 57 patients with surgical sepsis were included in the analysis. Among them, 22 patients died during ICU admission, giving an ICU mortality rate of 38.6%, while 35 patients survived (Figure 1). Most patients were male (84.2%). The median age of the overall patient was 48.0 years (IQR 37.0-58.0). Non-survivors were significantly older than survivors [58.0 (35.0-68.0) vs 47.0 (40.0-52.0), $p = 0.039$]. ICU stay was also significantly longer in non-survivors [10.0 (6.0-17.0) vs 6.0 (3.0-8.0), $p = 0.002$]. However, total hospital stay and postoperative hospital stay did not differ significantly between the two groups. Most patients underwent emergency surgery, and abdominal sepsis was the most common source of infection. Malignant disease and comorbid conditions were more common among non-survivors. Bloodstream infection was also more frequent in non-survivors and approached statistical significance (Table 1).

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

Table 1. Baseline characteristics and ICU outcome comparison.

Characteristic	Total (n=57)	Survivors (n=35)	Non-survivors (n=22)	P value
Age (years)	48.0 (37.0–58.0)	47.0 (40.0–52.0)	58.0 (35.0–68.0)	0.039
Male sex	48 (84.2%)	29 (82.9%)	19 (86.4%)	1.000
Emergency surgery	39 (68.4%)	25 (71.4%)	14 (63.6%)	0.746
Malignant pathology	12 (21.1%)	4 (11.4%)	8 (36.4%)	0.043
Any comorbidity	13 (22.8%)	4 (11.4%)	9 (40.9%)	0.021
Abdominal source	55 (96.5%)	33 (94.3%)	22 (100.0%)	0.518
Bloodstream source	14 (24.6%)	5 (14.3%)	9 (40.9%)	0.050
ICU stay (days)	7.0 (5.0–10.0)	6.0 (3.0–8.0)	10.0 (6.0–17.0)	0.002
ICU mortality	22 (38.6%)	0 (0.0%)	22 (100.0%)	

Figure 1. ICU outcome distribution.

Admission platelet count was lower in non-survivors than survivors, although the difference was not statistically significant [140.0 (104.0–222.0) vs 160.0 (133.0–380.0), $p = 0.222$]. In contrast, platelet nadir showed a strong relationship with ICU mortality. Non-survivors had a much lower platelet nadir than survivors [37.5 (20.0–81.5) vs 93.0 (79.0–165.5), $p < 0.001$]. In addition, the fall in platelet count from admission to nadir was significantly greater among non-survivors ($p = 0.027$). Mortality progressively increased as platelet nadir category worsened, with the highest mortality observed in patients with severe thrombocytopenia.

The timing of platelet nadir also differed significantly between the two groups. Survivors reached platelet nadir earlier, with a median time of 2.0 days (IQR 2.0–4.5), whereas non-survivors reached nadir later, at 6.0 days (IQR 4.0–8.0), $p < 0.001$ (Table 2). Serial platelet trend analysis demonstrated recovery of platelet counts among survivors, while non-survivors showed persistent decline without meaningful recovery (Figure 2).

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

Table 2. Platelet-related variables in survivors and non-survivors.

Platelet variable	Total (n=57)	Survivors (n=35)	Non-survivors (n=22)	P value
Admission platelet count ($\times 10^9/L$)	160.0 (120.0–254.0)	160.0 (133.0–380.0)	140.0 (104.0–222.0)	0.222
Platelet nadir ($\times 10^9/L$)	86.0 (25.0–135.0)	93.0 (79.0–165.5)	37.5 (20.0–81.5)	<0.001
Absolute fall in platelet count ($\times 10^9/L$)	-78.0 (-130.0–22.0)	-56.0 (-115.5–0.0)	-79.0 (-201.8–72.0)	0.027
Timing of platelet nadir, days from admission	4.0 (2.0-6.0)	2.0 (2.0-4.5)	6.0 (4.0-8.0)	<0.001

Figure 2. Platelet trend by ICU outcome.

Mortality increased progressively as platelet nadir category worsened (chi-square $p = 0.002$). Patients with severe thrombocytopenia (platelet nadir $<50 \times 10^9/L$) had the highest ICU mortality, with 11 of 15 patients dying (73.3%). Patients with moderate thrombocytopenia ($50-99 \times 10^9/L$) had an ICU mortality of 39.1% (9/23). In contrast, no deaths were observed among patients with mild thrombocytopenia

($100-149 \times 10^9/L$), while patients with normal platelet nadir ($\geq 150 \times 10^9/L$) had a relatively low ICU mortality of 15.4% (2/13) (Table 3). These findings demonstrate a clear relationship between worsening platelet nadir category and increasing ICU mortality.

Table 3. ICU mortality according to platelet nadir category.

Platelet nadir category	Total (n=57)	Survivors (n=35)	Non-survivors (n=22)	ICU mortality within group	P value (Chi-square)
Severe (<50)	15	4	11	73.3%	0.002
Moderate (50-99)	23	14	9	39.1%	
Mild (100-149)	6	6	0	0.0%	
Normal (≥ 150)	13	11	2	15.4%	

Admission WBC count was higher in non-survivors than survivors, but the difference was not statistically significant [$12.4 (8.3-18.0)$ vs $8.2 (7.6-14.5)$, $p = 0.113$]. However, peak WBC count was significantly higher in non-survivors

[$32.1 (26.4-42.2)$ vs $20.5 (15.7-30.9)$, $p = 0.002$]. The increase in WBC from admission to peak also tended to be greater among non-survivors and approached statistical significance ($p = 0.056$) (Table 4). Serial WBC trends

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

showed persistently elevated leukocyte counts among non-survivors, whereas survivors demonstrated relatively stable

values over time (Figure 3).

Table 4. WBC-related variables in survivors and non-survivors.

WBC variable	Total (n=57)	Survivors (n=35)	Non-survivors (n=22)	P value
Admission WBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	10.4 (7.6–15.2)	8.2 (7.6–14.5)	12.4 (8.3–18.0)	0.113
Peak WBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	26.4 (18.0–34.5)	20.5 (15.7–30.9)	32.1 (26.4–42.2)	0.002
Absolute rise in WBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	13.7 (6.4–19.4)	11.5 (6.3–19.1)	14.6 (13.5–29.8)	0.056
Timing of WBC peak, days from admission	4.0 (2.0–8.0)	3.0 (1.0–8.0)	6.0 (2.0–7.0)	0.569

Figure 3. WBC trend by ICU outcome.

Correlation analysis demonstrated weak overall relationships between platelet and WBC measures. Platelet nadir showed no significant correlation with peak WBC in the overall patients. However, platelet nadir demonstrated a significant positive correlation with admission WBC ($\rho = 0.325$, $p = 0.014$), and admission platelet count showed a modest positive correlation with peak WBC ($\rho = 0.275$, $p = 0.038$). Among survivors, platelet and WBC variables

generally showed positive correlations. In contrast, non-survivors demonstrated inverse relationships between several platelet and WBC measures, suggesting more severe inflammatory dysregulation (Table 5 and Figure 4-6).

Table 5. Spearman correlations between platelet and WBC measures.

Groups	Variable pair	Spearman rho	P value
Overall	Admission platelet vs admission WBC	0.136	0.314
	Platelet nadir vs peak WBC	-0.098	0.469
	Platelet nadir vs admission WBC	0.325	0.014
	Admission platelet vs peak WBC	0.275	0.038

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

Survivors	Admission platelet vs admission WBC	0.603	<0.001
	Platelet nadir vs peak WBC	0.340	0.046
	Platelet nadir vs admission WBC	0.735	<0.001
	Admission platelet vs peak WBC	0.227	0.190
Non-survivors	Admission platelet vs admission WBC	-0.691	<0.001
	Platelet nadir vs peak WBC	-0.617	0.002
	Platelet nadir vs admission WBC	0.104	0.645
	Admission platelet vs peak WBC	0.506	0.016

Figure 4. Admission platelet and platelet nadir by ICU outcome.

Figure 5. Admission WBC and peak WBC by ICU outcome.

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

Figure 6. Relationship between platelet nadir and peak WBC.

ROC analysis showed that dynamic hematologic markers had better prognostic performance than admission values. Platelet nadir had the highest predictive performance among platelet measures, with an AUC of 0.768 and an optimal cut-off value of $90.0 \times 10^9/L$ (sensitivity 90.9% and specificity 60.0%). Peak WBC had the highest predictive value among

leukocyte measures, with an AUC of 0.743 and an optimal cut-off value of $22.3 \times 10^9/L$ (sensitivity 86.4% and specificity 57.1%) (Table 6 and Figure 7). Admission platelet count and admission WBC had lower discriminatory ability.

Table 6. ROC-derived cut-offs for hematologic predictors of ICU mortality.

Biomarker	AUC	95% CI	Optimal cut-off	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	P value
Admission platelet	0.597	0.440–0.754	222.0	77.3	48.6	0.214
Platelet nadir	0.768	0.638–0.898	90.0	90.9	60.0	<0.001
Admission WBC	0.626	0.476–0.776	8.3	77.3	51.4	0.118
Peak WBC	0.743	0.611–0.875	22.3	86.4	57.1	0.002

Figure 7. ROC curves for ICU mortality.

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

These two dynamic thresholds were combined into a three-level hematologic risk group. The resulting gradient was clinically compelling: mortality was 0.0% in the low-risk group, 29.2% in the intermediate-risk group, and 71.4% in the high-risk group. The overall association between combined risk group and ICU mortality was highly significant ($p < 0.001$) (Table 7 and Figure 8). This

combined platelet-WBC model provided clinically meaningful risk stratification in surgical septic ICU patients. This finding suggests that platelets and WBC kinetics contain complementary information and may be more informative when interpreted jointly than individually.

Table 7. Association between combined platelet-WBC risk group and ICU mortality.

Combined platelet-WBC risk group	Total	Survivors	Non-survivors	ICU mortality within group	P value (Chi-square)
Low risk	12	12	0	0.0%	<0.001
Intermediate risk	24	17	7	29.2%	
High risk	21	6	15	71.4%	

Figure 8. ICU mortality by combined platelet-WBC risk group.

Overall, the findings suggest that serial hematologic trends are more useful than isolated admission values. Non-survivors were characterized by deeper platelet decline, delayed platelet nadir, and higher inflammatory response during ICU stay. These observations support routine longitudinal hematologic surveillance and dynamic risk interpretation in septic surgical patients.

DISCUSSION

The present study demonstrates that dynamic hematologic changes are more clinically important than admission laboratory values in surgical sepsis. Although admission platelet count and admission WBC count were higher or lower in expected directions, these baseline values alone did not clearly separate survivors from non-survivors. In contrast, platelet nadir and peak WBC showed much stronger associations with ICU mortality. These findings support the concept that serial laboratory trends provide

more prognostic information than single admission measurements.

Platelet abnormalities are common in sepsis and reflect complex interactions between inflammation, coagulation, endothelial injury, and immune response. During severe sepsis, platelets are consumed within the microcirculation and participate in inflammatory signaling pathways. Therefore, thrombocytopenia in septic patients is not simply a hematologic abnormality but also a marker of disease severity and physiologic deterioration (4,8). In this study, non-survivors developed significantly lower platelet nadir values than survivors, indicating more severe systemic dysfunction.

An important observation from this study was the timing of platelet nadir. Survivors generally reached their lowest platelet count early during ICU admission and subsequently demonstrated recovery. In contrast, non-survivors continued to show delayed platelet decline several days after ICU admission. This delayed nadir may indicate persistent

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

infection, inadequate source control, ongoing inflammatory activation, or progressive organ dysfunction. Clinically, continued platelet decline after the early ICU period should alert clinicians to possible deterioration even when admission platelet count appears acceptable.

The findings related to leukocyte response were also clinically meaningful. Admission WBC count alone did not significantly predict mortality. However, peak WBC count was significantly higher among non-survivors, suggesting that persistent or worsening inflammatory response plays an important role in poor outcome. In surgical sepsis, elevated WBC trends may reflect unresolved contamination, ongoing tissue necrosis, postoperative complications, or failure of adequate infection control (9-11).

Correlation analysis demonstrated that platelet count and WBC count are related but represent different biological aspects of sepsis. Survivors showed more positive relationships between platelet and WBC measures, which may reflect coordinated inflammatory recovery. In contrast, non-survivors demonstrated inverse relationships between several platelet and WBC variables, suggesting dysregulated host response and severe inflammatory imbalance. Although the sample size was relatively small, these findings support the concept that platelet consumption and leukocyte activation occur together during severe sepsis.

ROC analysis further strengthened the importance of dynamic markers. Platelet nadir demonstrated the best predictive performance among platelet variables, while peak WBC showed the best predictive ability among leukocyte variables. Both variables performed better than admission measurements. These findings are clinically important because platelet count and WBC count are inexpensive, routinely available, and easily repeatable investigations that can be monitored in all ICU settings, including resource-limited hospitals.

The combined platelet-WBC risk model was one of the most clinically useful findings of the study. Patients classified as low risk had no ICU mortality, whereas those in the high-risk group had mortality exceeding 70%. This simple bedside model may help clinicians identify patients who require closer monitoring, repeated imaging, reassessment of source control, escalation of organ support, and earlier multidisciplinary review. Importantly, this approach does not require expensive biomarkers or advanced technology.

The findings of this study are generally consistent with previous literature. Several studies have reported associations between thrombocytopenia and poor outcomes in sepsis. Similarly, previous research has demonstrated that WBC trends may provide better prognostic information than admission leukocyte counts alone. The present study adds to existing evidence by focusing specifically on surgical septic ICU patients and by combining platelet and WBC dynamics into a single practical risk model.

From a clinical perspective, this study emphasizes the importance of serial hematologic monitoring in surgical sepsis. Clinicians should not rely solely on admission platelet count or admission WBC count. Instead, careful attention should be paid to the depth of platelet decline, timing of platelet nadir, and persistence of leukocytosis during ICU stay. Patients with platelet nadir $\leq 90 \times 10^9/L$ together with peak WBC $\geq 22.3 \times 10^9/L$ should be considered high risk and evaluated carefully for ongoing sepsis and organ dysfunction.

This study has several limitations. It was a single-center hospital-based observational analytical study with a relatively small sample size. Severity scores such as SOFA score, lactate levels, vasopressor requirement, and microbiological burden were not included in the analysis. Therefore, the results should be interpreted cautiously and validated in larger prospective studies.

Despite these limitations, the study clearly demonstrates that serial platelet and WBC monitoring provides valuable prognostic information in surgical sepsis. Dynamic hematologic markers appear to be more useful than admission values alone and may strengthen bedside risk assessment in critically ill surgical patients.

CONCLUSION

In this study of surgical septic ICU patients, dynamic hematologic markers provided greater prognostic value than admission laboratory values alone. Platelet nadir was significantly lower, occurred later, and declined more markedly among non-survivors, while peak WBC was significantly higher in patients who died during ICU admission. ROC analysis identified platelet nadir and peak WBC as the strongest hematologic predictors of ICU mortality. The combined platelet-WBC risk model demonstrated clear mortality stratification and identified a high-risk subgroup with markedly increased ICU mortality. These findings support the routine use of serial platelet and WBC trend monitoring in surgical sepsis rather than reliance on single admission measurements. Overall, platelet trajectory and inflammatory response appear to reflect disease severity and ongoing septic burden in critically ill surgical patients. Combined interpretation of platelet nadir and peak WBC may therefore provide a simple, inexpensive, and practical bedside tool for ICU risk assessment and early clinical decision-making.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Serial monitoring of platelet count and WBC trends should be routinely performed in surgical septic ICU patients.
- Platelet nadir $\leq 90 \times 10^9/L$ and peak WBC $\geq 22.3 \times 10^9/L$ should be considered important high-risk indicators for ICU mortality.

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

- Persistent thrombocytopenia or elevated WBC during ICU stay should prompt reassessment for ongoing infection, organ dysfunction, or inadequate source control.
- Combined platelet-WBC risk stratification may serve as a simple and practical bedside prognostic tool in surgical sepsis.
- Larger prospective multicenter studies are recommended to validate these findings and confirm the proposed cut-off values.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the surgical team and ICU team for their exceptional expertise, dedication, and teamwork, which played a pivotal role in the successful completion of this study.

I would also like to express my deepest respect and heartfelt gratitude to Professor Dr. Samiran Nundy, Advisor, Institute of Surgical Gastroenterology, GI and HPB Onco-Surgery and Liver Transplantation, Delhi, India, for his invaluable mentorship, inspiration, and guidance during my fellowship period. His encouragement and academic leadership played a fundamental role in motivating me to begin surgical research and academic writing in my professional career. I am truly honored to acknowledge him as one of the most important mentors in my research journey.

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to Professor Dr. Khin Aung Htun, Professor Dr. Myo Thant, Professor Dr. Thant Lwyn San, and Dr. Than Htike Aung for their guidance, encouragement, and unwavering support throughout the course of this study.

I would like to extend my special gratitude and heartfelt thanks to Professor Dr. Khin Phyu Pyar, Professor, Senior Consultant Physician and Nephrologist, Former Head of Department of Medicine and Nephology, for her constant encouragement, generous support, and invaluable mentorship throughout my academic journey. Her mentorship has been instrumental in inspiring and motivating me to pursue and publish my surgical research, case reports, and case series, and I am truly honored to acknowledge her as my mentor.

I am also sincerely thankful to all my patients for their trust and participation, without whom this study would not have been possible.

I am profoundly grateful to my beloved wife, Dr. Zin Mar Myint Aung, Senior Consultant Microbiologist at Pyin Oo Lwin General Hospital, for her constant encouragement, understanding, patience, and unwavering support in conducting, completing, and publishing this study.

Finally, I would like to acknowledge all individuals and colleagues who contributed directly or indirectly to this research. Without the contributions of all those mentioned, the successful publication of this study would not have been possible.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declared no potential conflict of interests with respect to authorship and publication of this article.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

This study was approved by the Hospital Research and Ethical Review Committee from No. (1) Military Hospital (700 Bedded), Pyin Oo Lwin, Myanmar. The period allowed by the Ethical Review Committee was from 01.12.2024 to 31.1.2026. The informed consent of human participants was obtained in written form.

FUNDING

The authors received no specific funding for this study and publication of this article.

REFERENCES

- I. Singer, M., Deutschman, C.S., Seymour, C.W., et al. (2016) The Third International Consensus Definitions for Sepsis and Septic Shock (Sepsis-3). *JAMA*. 2016, 315(8): 801-810.
- II. Evans, L., Rhodes, A., Alhazzani, W., et al. (2021) Surviving Sepsis Campaign: international guidelines for management of sepsis and septic shock 2021. *Intensive Care Medicine*. 2021, 47(11): 1181-1247.
- III. Hotchkiss, R.S., Moldawer, L.L., Opal, S.M., Reinhart, K., Turnbull, I.R., and Vincent, J.L. (2016) Sepsis and septic shock. *Nat Rev Dis Primers*. 2016, 2: 16045.
- IV. Vardon-Bouines, F., Gratacap, M.P., Groyer, S., et al. (2019) Kinetics of mean platelet volume predicts mortality in patients with septic shock. *PLoS One*. 2019, 14(10): e0223553.
- V. Hua, Y., Ou, X., Li, Q., and Zhu, T. (2023) Platelet count predicts mortality in patients with sepsis: A retrospective observational study. *Frontiers in Medicine*. 2023, 102(38): e35335.
- VI. Mangalesh, S., Dudani, S., Dash, S.K., et al. (2021) Platelet indices and their kinetics predict mortality in patients with sepsis. *Indian Journal of Critical Care Medicine*. 2021, 25(6): 633-640.
- VII. Schupp, T., Weidner, T., et al. (2023) Diagnostic and prognostic role of platelets in patients with sepsis and septic shock. *Thrombosis and Haemostasis*. 2023, 34(1): 2131753.
- VIII. Burunsuzoglu, B., et al. (2016) Thrombocytopenia: a risk factor of mortality for patients with sepsis in the intensive care unit. *Turk Thorac*. 2016, 17: 7-14.
- IX. Rimmer, E., Houston, B.L., Kumar, A., et al. White blood cell count trajectory and mortality in septic shock: a historical cohort study. *Can J Anaesth*. 2022, 69(10): 1230-1239.

Importance of Dynamic Platelet Changes in Surgical Sepsis: Association with ICU Mortality and Correlation with White Blood Cell Count

- X. Tanaka H, Ikeda T, Shimizu T, et al. White blood cell counts have an impact on septic patient outcome followed by polymyxin-B immobilized fiber with direct hemoperfusion. *Crit Care*. 2015, 19(Suppl 1): P128.
- XI. Belok, S.H., et al. Evaluation of leukopenia during sepsis as a marker of sepsis-defining organ dysfunction. *PLoS One*. 2021, 16(6): e0252206.
- XII. Cato, L.D., et al. (2018) Platelet count: a predictor of sepsis and mortality in severe burns. *Burns*. 2018, 44(2): 288-297.
- XIII. Guclu, E., Durmaz, Y., and Karabay, O. (2013) Effect of severe sepsis on platelet count and their indices. *African Health Sciences*. 2013, 13(2): 333-338.
- XIV. He, Y., et al. (2023) The value of peripheral blood leukocyte parameters in the early diagnosis and clinical prognosis of sepsis. *Int J Anal Chem*. 2023, 6052085.
- XV. Asadollahi, K., Hastings, I.M., Beeching, N.J., and Gill, G.V. (2011) Leukocytosis as an alarming sign for mortality in patients hospitalized in general wards. *Iran J Med Sci*. 2011, 36(1): 45-49.
- XVI. Jarczak, D., Kluge, S., and Nierhaus, A. (2021) Sepsis-pathophysiology and therapeutic concepts. *Front in Med (Lausanne)*. 2021, 8: 628302.